

THE CONCEPT OF DISCOURSE AND ITS STUDY

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Introduction

Discourse is the subject of interdisciplinary research. In addition to theoretical linguistics, computer linguistics and artificial intelligence, psychology, philosophy and logic, sociology, anthropology and Ethnology, literature, semiotics, historiography, theology, law, pedagogy, translation theory and practice, politics and other discourse-related fields of Science and research are also the main objects of study. Each of these disciplines approaches the study of discourse in its own way.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The social sciences and humanities define discourse as a formed mindset expressed through language. It is the way society thinks and communicates about people, things and social organization, as well as the relationship between these three elements. Sociology considers discourse to be a way of giving meaning to reality. Political science understands this as a formal logical exchange of ideas for solving a social problem. Psychological discourse evaluates the form and function of language in writing or verbally, as they are related to mental health.

In the field of rhetoric, discourse has a slightly different meaning, that is, Speakers convince their audience of the inherent perception of reality. Rhetorical discourse involves a central, regulatory voice - speaking or narrating person-who tries to encourage listeners to come to a conclusion that serves the speaker's purposes. Rhetorical discourse uses only narrative elements to convince the reader or listener; they are rarely complete stories. The goal here is to convince, not aesthetic, didacticism or poetic expression.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The application of the concept of discourse in semantics is more complex. Discourse semantics is the analysis of how we use vocabulary in specific areas of intellectual research. This analysis explores the connection between language and structure, such as the relationship between a sentence and the broader

context in which it exists. An example of this is the use of a pronoun in a sentence, which the reader or listener can only understand while connected.

In terms of modern approaches, discourse is a complex communicative phenomenon, which, in addition to text, includes additional linguistic factors (thoughts, knowledge of the World, goals, attitudes of the recipient) necessary for understanding the text.

The term "discourse" has also become one of the very commonly used terms in linguistics. Historically, the term was first coined by the American linguist Z. Harris's paper "discursive analysis", published in 1952, was used. The full scope of the term "discourse" has become more popular in linguistics over the past twenty years.

Linguist A. According to Pardaev's interpretation, discourse is the process of practical use of linguistic and nonlinear means by the speaker and the listener in a form and type that they consider most effective for the purpose of exchanging ideas, influencing each other. Discourse is a process, a type of human activity. It is the realization of the linguistic and hundreds of nonlinear factors in a common form towards one goal. In another source, discursus is derived from the Latin word "discursus" - discussion, meaning emotional, direct, intuitive, that is, logical proof - proof knowledge, which is generated by means through discussion, as opposed to discussion-demand knowledge. More simply, in this definition, the meaning of discourse discussing, talking is put forward.

Discourse in Uzbek linguistics Special Studies linguist Sh. Performed by Safarov. The linguist notes the following about the problems of text and discourse: "if both text and discourse are the result of human linguistic activity, I have the suspicion of being able to distinguish them only by the qualities of "oral" and "written", based on the apparent - formal indicator. Just as well, it is a difficult matter to imagine one of them in a material-looking phenomenon, the other in a way that is devoid of this property. After all, when both of these things become the product of a productive activity, is it necessary that the achieved result takes on a material appearance? The purposefully expressed communicative content and the informative content generated in the listener's perception (perception) without association with the speaker's desire do not negate each other, but instead become a factor that interweaves, merges and ensures the effectiveness of communication. The homogeneity of communicative and informative content ensures the integrity of the macrobity of the communication system. Currently, it is recognized that such a feature of integrity has only a discursive one.

Ye.S.Kubryakova kaydicha, "there is no generally accepted definition of discourse in the era of the current development of linguistics"

In linguistics, discourse refers to a language unit that is longer than one sentence. The word discourse is derived from the Latin prefix dis - meaning "far away" and the stem "currere" meaning "to walk". Therefore, speech is translated as "escape" and means how the conversation goes. Speech learning is the analysis of the use of oral or written language in a social context. Discourse studies consider the shape and function of a language in speech in addition to its small grammatical parts, such as phonemes and morphemes. This field of study, in which the Dutch linguist Teun van Dijk played an important role in development, explores how large units of language, including lexemes, syntax, and context, add meaning to conversations.

"Discourse in context can consist of only one or two words, such as "smoking is prohibited" or "stop". Alternatively, part of the speech may consist of hundreds of thousands of words, as in some novels. The normal volume of discourse is located between the two dimensions, as above.

"Discourse is the social application of language to convey a broad historical meaning. It is a language that is determined by the social conditions of its application, Who and under what conditions it is used. Language can never be "neutral" because it serves to connect our personal and social worlds. "

The importance of discourse in literature. Speech of any kind is one of the most important elements of human behavior and formation. There have been many studies on how the brain converts thoughts into words and, of course, communication shapes the brain. Many studies focus on the different ways in which speakers of different languages understand concepts. Thus, the creation and dissemination of speech is most important for the eternity of the human race. Literature is one of the main ways to preserve speech and create new ways of understanding the world. By reading artistic discursive patterns from other cultures and other eras, we can better understand what their authors think. Indeed, reading literature from our own beautiful cultures can better emphasize our ways of thinking and interacting. Since every work of literature created is an example of discourse, our understanding of artistic discourse is essential for our understanding of literature. [6]

Types of artistic discourses. There are different views among Western scholars on artistic discourse and its types. When someone uses language to communicate, they use discourse. Hence, the writer's work relies primarily on discourse to tell stories, exchange ideas, and disseminate information. In fact,

there is no literature without discourse either. However, not all discourse is the same, literary scholars divide it into four main types: argument, description, explanation, and narrative.

Argument. The argument is an attempt to convince the reader through logic and reasoning. The writer makes a clear claim and then presents evidence to support this claim. For example, academic essays use argumentative speech to convince readers of the truth of the general thesis.

Description. The description is an emotional experience for the reader, which helps to develop clear mental images of the information provided. Novels, short stories and poems depend on the power of the image that excites and excites the reader.

Exposition. The exhibition notifies the viewer of a certain fact, but does not seek to influence the opinion of the audience about this fact. Visual speech is neutral in language and tone so as not to convince the reader or provoke emotions; its purpose is only information. News stories and other publicistic articles, comparative analysis, and other research-oriented literature generally use exposure.

Story. The story is a written explanation that presents the story to the reader. In other words, This Is The Voice of the narrator. The story captivates the reader through an attractive language that evokes emotion and empathy, and keeps the reader scrolling through the page. The story is the basis for novels, short stories and some plays.

Other schools of thought classify literary speech into the categories of expressive, poetic and transactional speech.

Expressive. Expressive speech reflects the feelings of the writer. Its focus is on the development and discussion of ideas, with little or no emphasis on specific facts, or attempts to convince others of Central evidence. Expressive works of speech have always been non-fiction; diaries and magazines, blogs and memoirs are examples of this.

Poetic. Poetic speech is a highly creative approach to writing fiction. The writer presents thoughts, emotions, events, places and characters in a fantastic, sometimes rhythmic language that attracts the emotions of readers. Poetic discourse emphasizes subject matter, image, and emotion. It is a central component of poetry, but it also manifests itself to some extent in most novels and short stories.

Transactional. Transactional discourse is a less literary, more instructive approach. It defines a specific action or plan, usually in an active voice, that

forces the reader to act. Advertising and marketing records, manuals and business correspondence are common sources of transaction speech.

Conclusion

Scientific sources also note that special scientific conferences were held on the solution of this problem. Such scientific research and the different views expressed in relation to the problem indicate that there are aspects of the issue of dialogical discourse that need to be solved in linguistics, in need of research.

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